

The Olympus Compute Cluster

The Olympus High Performance Compute Cluster located at the Pittsburgh Supercomputing Center at Carnegie Mellon University, and is supported by National Institute of General Medical Sciences Modeling Infectious Disease Agent Study (MIDAS) Informatics Services Group grant 1U24GM110707.

Olympus provides a flexible, multiple-use compute cluster with several specialized partitions to accommodate a variety of workloads including: extremely high memory multi-threaded applications, tightly coupled message-passing applications, trivially-parallel, and serial batch jobs.

Additional information can be found at:

- <https://www.psc.edu/resources/computing/olympus>
- https://git.isg.pitt.edu/hpc/olympus/wikis/machine_description

Hardware

The Olympus cluster consists of 66 execution hosts (i.e. nodes) and 13 'Application Servers' which run system services, export the cluster filesystems, and host several virtualized login nodes.

Olympus contains two distinct node types. Approximately half of the cluster is based on AMD Opteron 6300 processors, and the other half utilizes Intel Xeon Ex v3 Series processors. Both node types are managed by the same batch scheduler.

Hardware Details

Processor Information

Count	Names	Model Name	CPU Freq. (GHz)	Physical Cores
6	n001-n006	AMD Opteron 6376	2.3	64 (64)
18	n007-n023,n025	AMD Opteron 6376	2.3	64 (64)
1	n024	AMD Opteron 6376	2.3	32 (32)
20	r001-r020	Intel Xeon E5-2695 v3	2.3	28 (56)

20	r021-r040	Intel Xeon E5-2695 v3	2.3	28 (56)
1	l001	Intel Xeon E7-8860 v3	2.2	56 (128)

Intel Xeon Nodes (r and l nodes)

The Intel Xeon nodes in Olympus offer three different memory configurations (128GB, 256GB, and 1TB) and feature both Gigabit and Intel OmniPath (100Gb) networking. Due to the high speed of the OmniPath network, these nodes are best suited for tightly-coupled applications using distributed-memory parallelism. In addition, the Olympus Intel nodes access an 80TB Lustre filesystem over OmniPath, resulting in very low I/O latency and high streaming performance. This filesystem is mounted at `/mnt/lustre0` and exposed via the `$WORK2` environment variable by the `io` module.

Intel Xeon E5-2695v3 Nodes (r nodes)

Each node has two multi-core processors and each processor has 14 physical compute cores. These processors support Intel's hyper-threading technology, thus each processor can utilize 28 logical compute cores for a total of 56 available cores per node. The PBS Torque batch scheduler exposes all 56 logical cores for scheduling. Note that it may be advantageous for some applications to schedule double the required number of cores (or the entire node) to ensure that dedicated physical cores are available to the running job. Nodes `r001-r020` offer 128GB of memory, while nodes `r021-r040` offer 256GB of memory.

Intel Xeon E7-8860v3 Large Memory Node (l001 node)

This node has four multi-core processors and each processor has 16 physical compute cores. These processors support Intel's hyper-threading technology, thus each processor can utilize 32 logical compute cores for a total of 128 available cores per node. The PBS Torque batch scheduler exposes all 128 logical cores for scheduling. Note that it may be advantageous for some applications to schedule double the required number of cores (or the entire node) to ensure that dedicated physical cores are available to the running job. This node features 1TB of physical memory.

AMD Opteron Nodes (n nodes)

Each node has four multi-core processors and each processor has 16 compute cores, for a total of 64 compute cores per node and 1536 compute cores overall. There are three different memory partitions (512GB, 256GB, and 128GB) and a total of 7.75 TB of aggregate memory.

Each node runs a 64-bit CentOS 7 operating system and all nodes are connected to one another by Gigabit Ethernet. There are multiple shared, cluster filesystems available across all nodes, and each node has locally mounted disk space.